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SECURITIES AS A SOURCE OF FINANCING INVESTMENT PROJECTS

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***Abstract.** Before proceeding to a direct consideration of the problems that arise during the work of financial institutions in the securities market, it is necessary to briefly characterize the current economic situation, the trends and directions in which it is evolving. From the variety of processes and institutional transformations currently taking place in the economy, it is necessary to single out those that have the most significant impact on the operations of financial institutions with securities. Determining the directions and mechanisms of such influences will make it possible to understand and formulate a number of provisions regarding the peculiarities of the participation of financial institutions in issuing securities dictated by the economic environment.*

***Keywords:** source of financing investment, economic environment, financial institutions, financial markets.*

INTRODUCTION

Before proceeding to a direct consideration of the problems that arise during the work of financial institutions in the securities market, it is necessary to briefly characterize the current economic situation, the trends and directions in which it is evolving. From the variety of processes and institutional transformations currently taking place in the economy, it is necessary to single out those that have the most significant impact on the operations of financial institutions with securities. Determining the directions and mechanisms of such influences will make it possible to understand and formulate a number of provisions regarding the peculiarities of the participation of financial institutions in issuing securities dictated by the economic environment.

Institutional transformations are primarily associated with a change in the structure of ownership, namely with the privatization of most of the state property. Privatization provides for the transformation of large and inefficient enterprises into open joint-stock companies. The issue of shares of such companies was supposed to be placed among their employees, partly to be sold at specialized auctions, part remained

in the ownership of the state. This variant of privatization led to the emergence of a market for the shares of privatized enterprises and the emergence of competition for controlling stakes in many of them and the strengthening of the role of financial institutions in them.

Another variant of institutional reforms was associated with attempts to overcome the legacy of the planned distribution economy. At the same time, one of the most important conditions for the survival of market entities was the diversification of the activities of enterprises and, consequently, the formation of the first stage of a market economy, which was characterized by the inevitable process of integrating disparate industries into single economic complexes, whether on the basis of merging into one joint-stock company or on the basis of financial and industrial groups. Now both possible processes are directly based on share ownership and the movement of shares (their exchange, purchase and sale, etc.).

It is important in a dynamically changing internal and external situation to pay attention to the sequence of formation of a market institutional structure in various sectors of the economy. It is obvious that the sphere, in which market transformations began earlier, with comparable amounts of financial power, increased activity in relation to other spheres, trying to involve them in the orbit of their influence.

Consequently, the current economic situation affecting the functioning of financial markets is characterized by the following features:

- decline in production;
- lack of liquid resources in the non-financial sector of the economy, expressed in a non-payment crisis;
- an increase in inflation;
- massive government borrowing in the financial market through securities;
- formation of a new institutional structure of the economy on the basis of joint stock ownership.

Along with this, the specifics of their organization, namely their number, the degree of their concentration, the prevailing organizational and legal form, the ownership structure and, of course, the regulatory guidelines governing the activities of financial institutions in the securities market, have an important impact on the operations of financial markets in the securities market. .

These factors, affecting the functioning of the financial market as a whole, cannot but determine the direction of their operations with securities, since the goals of the latter depend on the goals facing the financial market as a whole.

Each of the factors we have noted affects the financial market and the activities of investment funds in the securities market.

A reduction in production volumes can create an economic situation in which, on the one hand, the risk of non-fulfillment of contractual obligations increases, and on the other hand, shrinking effective demand reduces the possibility of effective implementation of investment projects through the issuance

of securities. In the case of banks, this means that lending to end borrowers is becoming an extremely risky business at the same time that the demand for loans from relatively reliable borrowers is decreasing.

In the context of preventing the negative consequences of the global financial and economic crisis, a way out can only be provided on an innovative basis, the transition to which requires long-term financial investments, including bank loans, the need for which is quite large. Modern financial institutions, for a number of reasons, which will be discussed below, are not able to satisfy this need. A number of financial institutions avoid lending, freeing up resources for operations in other sectors of the financial market, including operations with securities.

The global financial and economic crisis, being one of the sides of the decline in production, which for a number of reasons has not found its resolution, in many respects has an impact similar to the recession on the banking system. At the same time, the global financial and economic crisis has led to the emergence of some specific transactions conducted by financial institutions in the financial market using securities.

The global financial and economic crisis contributed to the emergence of a rapidly growing debt market. In many CIS countries, this crisis has led to the emergence of many payments for products received, on the other hand, the growth in the volume of securities issued by banks to use them as lending instruments. For reasons related to the enormous risks of non-payment, a number of bank operations with enterprises have not received significant distribution (for example, operations on bill crediting of enterprises).

In conditions of growth or often fluctuating inflation, it becomes profitable to invest for the shortest possible time, even agreeing to a lower interest rate, while gaining, however, due to the speed of turnover.

Inflation also affects the investment qualities of types of securities, i.e. shares and bonds. So, the fundamental rule of investing says: the higher the level of interest rates in the economy, the lower the market value of shares. This applies both to the shares of the banks themselves, reducing the possibility of strengthening the capital base, and to the shares of joint stock companies.

As a result, under the influence of inflation, transactions with securities, both in terms of placement and in terms of attracting resources, are of a pronounced short-term nature.

An important influence on the behavior of banks is exerted by the policy pursued by the state to cover the state budget deficit by issuing debt securities. This influence manifests itself both directly through the accumulation of free funds of banks, and indirectly through the impact on interest rates. The yield on government securities determines the minimum required level of rates for active operations, primarily lending. On loans, as a rule, interest rates are always set at a significantly higher level than the yield on government securities with similar maturities, since with equal yields, obviously, preference will be given to a more reliable, liquid, tax-friendly instrument - government securities.

Increasingly relying on the securities market in solving budgetary problems, the state is forced to constantly increase the volume of issuance of securities, the implementation of which is achieved most

often by offering higher interest rates. The state thus artificially contributes to the growth of rates on other financial instruments, primarily loans. It becomes more difficult for banks to find bona fide borrowers who are able to implement profitable projects with the help of expensive loans. As a result, money again has to be invested in government securities.

Consequently, the policy of extensive domestic borrowing carried out by the state leads to the fact that more and more bank resources are involved in transactions with government securities.

The process of institutionalizing the structure of production, adequate to the requirements of a market economy, which began on the basis of a joint-stock form of ownership, made it possible for financial institutions to actively participate in it. In particular, the participation of banks in the transformation of the sphere of material production is all the more relevant, since the banking sector, earlier than the production sector, switched to market principles and managed to adapt to them in terms of working methods, organizational structure and ownership structure.

The participation of banks in the transformation of the manufacturing sector is the acquisition of a significant stake in the voting shares of enterprises that are of interest to the bank. Thus obtaining a certain control over the activities of enterprises, banks use their, as a rule, much broader opportunities to find sources for financing investment projects implemented at these enterprises. We are talking about both the provision of loans and assistance in obtaining financing from other sources, including from foreign investors.

Let us now dwell on the peculiarities of the organization of the system of financing influencing the activities of financial institutions in the securities market. Securities transactions are affected by the weak concentration of financial market institutions. Thus, as of January 1, 2012, the brokerage offices of banks carried out exchange transactions in the amount of 50.4 billion soums, which exceeds the same indicator for 2010 (21.3 billion soums) by almost two and a half times (see Table 1).

Table 1. Participation of brokerage houses of banks in exchange trading¹

	Banks that have accredited brokerage houses	2010			2011		
		Number of transactions	Amount of transactios (million soums)	Share in turnover of brokerage houses(%)	Number of transactions	Amount of transactions (million soums)	Share in turnover of brokerage houses(%)

¹ Calculated based on the materials of the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent". Results for 2011.

1	National bank of Uzbekistan	1	4,1	0,003	2	35660,2	8,4
2	Bank "Ipak Yuli"	22	5712,7	4,4	38	11198,3	3,6
3	Hamkorbank	162	4629,7	3,6	90	2678,9	0,6
4	Bank Asaka	2	1754,9	1,4	1	650,00	0,2
5	Kapital Bank	39	9150,0	7,1	3	188,2	0,04
6	Agrobank	-	-	-	-	-	-
	TOTAL	226	21251,4	16,5	134	50367,6	11,8

As follows from the data in Table 1, commercial banks are the most active participants in the stock market, acting at the auctions of the Republican Stock Exchange "Tashkent" both as issuers of securities and as investors. Despite this, other commercial banks are unable to ensure the transparency of the securities market.

The weak concentration of bank capital often reduces the effectiveness of commercial banks' participation in the equity capital of enterprises to a minimum. Another consequence of weak concentration is the fact that many commercial banks, due to scarce financial resources, cannot find options for relatively reliable lending, preferring to invest in government securities.

So, summarizing the above, we can draw conclusions regarding the specifics of the operations of financial institutions in the securities market.

Huge interest rate risks and high inflation have led to the fact that these transactions have a pronounced short-term nature.

For a number of reasons (government policy to cover the state budget deficit, weak concentration of capital of commercial banks), resources in significant and ever-increasing volumes are involved in transactions with government securities.

Crisis factors affecting the activities of subjects in the sphere of material production contributed to the widespread operations of commercial banks using short-term lending operations.

The conditions for the structural design of the sphere of material production on the basis of joint-stock ownership pushed commercial banks to participate in this area through the acquisition of shares.

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